

Youth Ambassador Transcript

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FN: Let's start with the simple. Tell me a bit about your role, how you got connected to this conference and in what capacity you participate, and if you like, how this could pertain to negotiation.

AV: I'm originally coming from the Kherson city in the South of Ukraine. I was living in occupied city for six months, and afterwards I went through Crimea, Russia, and Belarus until I ended up in Berlin, where I am partly living as well as in Prague. These experiences influenced my views and my focus in my work right now, because I faced horrors of war in the first hand. So, for me it is important to share the views in my career.

Currently, I'm studying International Relations and Diplomacy at the Prague University of Economics and Business. At the same time, since 2023, I have the honor to be Young European Ambassador from Neighbors East, representing Ukraine on international stage. I'm also working together with Ukrainian Embassy in Prague, and serve as the Head of the Horizon European Research Program. Currently, the focus of our project is to examine the disinformation in Central Europe – specifically how Russian narratives influence the current electoral campaign in the Czech Republic. We will conduct interviews in three different categories. Politicians, diplomats, and ordinary civilians to combine all of this together. With these high-level participants, I believe that this project can have a real impact.

I'm also the director of European programs, leading Erasmus Plus programs for non-formal education for young people. It's what I do in Berlin with projects all over Europe. There, I serve as facilitator and tutor, and I lead these programs and grant proposals as well. I believe it's how non-formal education can have an impact on people from the various countries. The idea of Erasmus Plus is to bring people together from all around the world, giving them topics for discussion in a learning environment. But also, to let them exchange their knowledge, pushing the boundaries of the social bubbles people are living in. I believe it is something truly great, and it's something that should be implemented in secondary education. It's what we're trying to roll out right now in the Netherlands.

FN: For how long are you doing external representation and inter-European communication?

AV: I'm Young European Ambassador since 2023 and work for Erasmus around two and half years. And I began writing the grant proposal and was really lucky to be in an environment with likeminded people. And I had so many ideas how we can work with marginalized youth and refugees mostly, and do something really impactful for them. We are focusing a lot on integration into European society for people from different countries.

44 **FN:** Can you expand on your role within Ukraine and what you're work with
45 the media?

46 **AV:** I'm collaborating with various Ukrainian media outlets on different
47 projects. However, I'm not working inside Ukraine since I'm living in
48 Prague and in Berlin, where I have family. So, I'm traveling a lot.
49 Together with the Ukrainian Embassy in Prague we un humanitarian-aid
50 project with partners in Ukraine and the ones that have relocated to
Europe.

51 **FN:** Do I understand correctly, that you try to convey the message of what
52 is going on and your experiences especially outside of the Ukraine?

53 **AV:** I truly believe that is needed, because Ukrainian international
54 presence in terms of media, it's absolutely not enough in comparison what
55 is really happening in Ukraine. Because the majority of my family living in
56 Ukraine are facing the war day by day. It is my responsibility and my
57 chance to be heard by people that could truly make a change. To convey
58 these realities and create empathy. Because the statistics in the news are
59 absolutely not enough. I think it is a big problem that Ukraine lacks the
60 media presence in Europe. Currently, the media mainly relies on data
61 provided by the administration. But I believe it is necessary to hear
62 personal stories. A third of Ukraine is occupied right now. And no one
63 knows the horror stories that people experience every day.

64 People usually ask me, if Kherson is still occupied. How it is going there?
65 And it's hard to explain, because the city is not occupied, but the Kherson
66 region is much bigger. It is still a gray zone an and there's almost no
67 chance for the people living there to tell about the terrors of the Russian
68 regime. They don't have the internet connection, because Ukrainian data is
69 not available there. I could not even believe that this is possible. But
70 yes, it is. They are providing their own data. And you will never find
71 something in Ukrainian language there. They are putting their national
72 channels on TV. Let's say you are a person over 60 and you're turning on
73 the TV, because it's only one resource of information that you can possibly
74 find. There are no movies, but only Russian news, and this is by purpose.

75 They run Russian schools. Children in these occupied areas can't study in
76 Ukrainian schools, not even online. It's forbidden and if you get caught
77 you face severe consequences. In fact, it is a huge responsibility for me
78 to get this message delivered to Europeans. For people to understand the
79 situation, especially the genocide. I was mentioning it during the session
80 here at the conference as well, because it's something I experience. People
81 that were studying with me in Kherson, they and many more just
disappeared

82 without a trace. We don't know. Their families don't know what happened to
83 them. I lost friends. They were murdered by Russian troops. When you think
84 about that, it's not anymore stories from the media, the statistics of
85 casualties per day, or something that you usually read in European media.
86 It's reality. It's happening and it's not far away from Europe. This is why
87 it's so important for my European colleagues to understand the Ukrainian
88 case and to understand how they can have influence on the Ukrainian
89 situation.

90 **FN:** In the best-case scenario, what is your goal to reach, especially with

91 the European partners you're cooperating with?

..2.1. European

92 **AV:** This is a big question. Because it is an ongoing war. Every day the
93 situation is radically changing and it's not something that you can predict.
94 So, I wouldn't say that I have some specific plans for cooperation. But I
95 know people working in my field, and I can connect them with Ukrainian
96 partners to start collaborations. As we do with the humanitarian aid
97 program. We're working with Rise Against Hunger organization in Italy, one
98 of the biggest humanitarian aid organizations that supplies huge amounts
of

99 these boxes and everything that's really needed. I established a connection
100 with an organization called Koridor Logistics between the Czech Republic
101 and Ukraine. It is really complicated because they are supplying that not
102 only to Ukraine, but directly to the battlefield. In the areas of the gray
zone, in really dangerous areas. This is a very specific case. I had the
103 opportunity to work with the embassy and to connect all of these three
104 organizations to do something, to act and to have the results. They were
105 really friendly and they were so happy that we established this cooperation
106 because they were looking for something like that from their side as well.
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108 **FN:** So, it's also about connecting people and to have this narrative of
109 what is actually happening on an individual basis, spread and disseminate
110 through Europe and also through the media landscape.

..1.2. Social

..1.1. Geopolitical

111 **AV:** Yes, to have at least a small outcome. Because I believe it's also a
112 lot about the society itself. Like, when the full-scale invasion started in
113 2022. It was really inspiring for me how people started to create the
114 groups. How they started to unite, no matter where they are from. From the
115 north or from the south the disagreements did not matter anymore. They
were
116 confronted with this one problem that they have to solve. Because Ukraine
117 is a huge country. Different views, different religion, different political
118 ideologies and so on. But when the war began, people started to create
NGOs.

119 That never happened before in this quantity. People started to be united
120 and create this civil-society movements. It was really powerful.

121 I experienced the same in my city with people who had no experience with
122 civil-society movements and some never heard of NGOs. They just knew
the

123 problem and that they need to solve it. And how can you solve it? By
124 uniting people. When people are united it is power. That was inspiring. I
125 believe by small steps we can achieve something and I don't want to take
126 the credits. I have a lot of people who are working with me in the same
127 process. We are communicating with people, we are connecting them. We
are

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128 providing our own projects. And I'm really glad that I have this
129 opportunity. Colleagues provided us with methods to achieve this goal. I
130 have an idea and we write the proposals and we implement them. It is truly
131 inspiring to be part of this collective and to inform political decisions
132 on different levels.

133 **FN:** The unification against a common enemy can be very powerful. If you
134 compare this unity to your work with the European partners and especially
135 also with what you experienced from the European Union and how they
react

136 to the crisis in Ukraine. What are the biggest hurdles that you have to
137 overcome? What is something where you notice this is a brick wall until
now
138 that you get against?

..2.1. European [139 **AV:** I would say in such a big union of countries there are many completely
140 different views. The decision-making process takes a lot of time. Because
141 of the diversity of views of European leaders which creates a lot of
142 complexity. To achieve something, all of them have to agree and have a
143 similar vision. This is regularly delaying the process that we try to
..2.1. European [144 achieve. When people are having different views, they have their own
145 interests, they have their own values. And I really regret to say this, but
146 it's disappointing sometimes to look at the situation and to see how slow
147 the process is.

148 And when they take into account practical issues or their own interests, I
149 understand it's important. But no one is talking about the people actually
150 living there. About the human beings, about the casualties, about human
..2.1. European [151 rights. As a Ukrainian living in the European Union, I think it is about
152 unity. It's something that we have to follow by heart. But this
153 decision-making process is making everything slow. I understand there is
154 bureaucracy and that it takes a lot of time to agree to all of it. But is
155 still delaying the real decision-making process.

156 **FN:** I understand that the administrative system of the European Union can
157 be frustrating. But if you look in the last two years, which I would argue
158 saw quite a development in Ukraine. And quite a development in the
European
159 Union, and the US with Trump's election. Do you see a change in the way
160 these topics get negotiated? And how much people actually listen to what
161 you have to say?

..1.1. Geopolitical [162 **AV:** First thing coming to my mind is the role the European Union wants to
163 play with the recent visit of their leaders in Ukraine. The same after the
164 election of Friedrich Merz. It demonstrated how the European countries
want
165 to show that Europe is taking part. Them visiting Kiev to show that they
166 also have influence. I feel like, they want to take charge. They want to
167 take part in this process. That was really important for Ukrainian
168 colleagues to see that their European colleagues are able to make
decisions.

..1.1. Geopolitical [169 That they want to be part of the process. And I think since 2022 a lot has
170 changed. Especially the amount of military aid European partners are
171 supplying. We are really grateful to have this opportunity. Because we have
172 to fight for our freedom. And many countries such as Germany - where you
173 from - supply a lot of ammunition and constantly support our country.
When
174 the war started, I was not sure if we could count on humanitarian aid, also
175 in regard to the reconstruction process.

176 That is really important. It is really visible. It was a decision made when
177 the war just started. And they've seen the destruction and all the horrors
178 and they decided that they have to take action. They want to have the
179 influence in the region as well. It was truly inspiring when different
180 European countries took responsibility for individual cities. Right now,
181 they are coordinating and collaborating in this context. And I think it's

182 really important what we retain this achievement in the future. Because
183 it's not one year program. It's not something that would not even be
184 accomplished in next even ten years. For the reconstruction it will require
185 at least 15 years. This is a huge amount of time. We have to think about
186 the process itself and how Europe will have impact in the region. Even
187 countries who is currently collaborating with some Ukrainian cities. They
188 have the exchange of the students. They have exchange of the business
189 developments. It's win-win situation for them. And I mean for sure it's
190 really valuable for us to have these partners right now in the region.

191 **FN:** Yes, absolutely. So, it seems to be a slow and maybe a bit dragging
192 process. But do you feel like it's going in the right direction?

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193 **AV:** Yes because when we have seen what happened with American donors
194 and supply of humanitarian aid. Ukraine was getting a lot of like financial
195 help from US. Right now, all of this is basically cut off. And we need a
196 replacement for it. For operating in advance also in terms of military
197 collaboration between Ukraine and European countries. It's really important
198 to develop European manufacturing at the same time, to implement this
199 technology and supply it to Ukrainian battlefields.

200 **FN:** Amazing. It's interesting that you have like all of these experiences
201 in such a short time. If you think back to all the conversations you had.
202 The negotiations with different stakeholders. Is there something that comes
203 to your mind that was the most demanding? Where you really noticed like
204 that this is hard to get through.

..3.1. Case Description

205 **AV:** Maybe I will give the example. Before coming here I've been to
206 conference in Brussels. In European social committee and European
207 commission. The discussions were related to climate change. I was
208 speaking about the ecocide in Ukraine after the Kakhovka Dam. Afterwards we were
209 speaking about the military aid. That we have to implement green energy to
210 produce Ukrainian ammunition. That we have to use sustainable energy in the
211 Ukrainian army. It's actually a great example for your previous question
212 regarding the decision-making processes. Sometimes when people are
213 sitting somewhere in offices in Brussels. They do not fully realize the context of
214 the situation.

..3.1.1. Challenge

..2.1. European

215 I'm extremely sorry to say this. But Ukraine is currently using the
216 military aid and ammunition, that was basically used by Europeans in the
217 second world war. And this ammunition required still required renovation
218 and so on. This is not the time to speak about green energy. Again,
219 ignoring the human-being factor, the human-right factor. I understand, the
220 event was about climate change. We were talking about the emissions and
221 so on. But no one pointed to the human lives of people who are currently dying
222 there. I was talking about the ecocide in Black Sea region. Because it's
223 not only impacting the south of Ukraine. It's having a huge and impact on
224 the whole Black Sea region. For all of these countries. Also in regards to
225 temperature regulations. It's already having the impact. And it will have
226 the impact in future on the average temperature in the region. It will have
227 impact on Europe as well. But unfortunately, no one is talking about that.

..1.3. Climate

228 This topic is not really on the agenda right now.

229 **FN:** I was hoping cross-border risks were already established by Pripyat.
230 Maybe it wasn't. How do you deal with this? How do you deal with
ignorance?

231 What are your strategies for yourself and your communications?

..5.1. Essential Skills

232 **AV:** I mean, I'm trying to bring the facts to the table. Because when you
233 show the real situation, many colleagues do not have the image of what is
234 truly happening. Frankly, I would say that I'm just showing the facts.

..3.1.1. Challenges

235 However, the statistics and data can never be accurate. Let's take the
236 south part of Ukraine or eastern part of Ukraine that are currently under
237 the Russian occupation. You can't have the accurate data from there. It's
238 quite complicated. This phrase might be overused, but you can't get this
239 data. So, I try to convey the context frame by frame.

..3.1.2. Outcome Deter

240 I have different strategies to make people look at them. How it is
241 impacting European perspective as well as the European future. When we
are
242 talking about climate it's also like not about only Ukraine. But we are
243 still like living not far away from each other. And it will have the impact
244 now and in the future. Not only talking about ammunition but no one is
245 mentioning missiles and their emissions. And no one mentions the
casualties
246 either. Everyone is talking about the different aspects. I mean it's great
247 to have implementation of the green energy into the tanks. We will be more
248 than happy to have this opportunity. But unfortunately, due to the
249 financial restraints it's currently not possible.

250 **FN:** As I understand it of course there's always an approximation. You
251 cannot collect clear data in a war zone. There's just no way to do that.
252 But I feel like we can have an educated guess. I would say on the research
253 side we are pretty clear on what is happening and how these consequences
254 are going to look. But there seems to be this gap between what we know in
255 research, what the politicians do and what especially the civil society in
256 Europe thinks. What would you suggest to bridge this gap?

..4.3. Bridging Strateg

257 **AV:** I think it is simple storytelling. When people not only rely on
258 statistics and the shape of graphs but hear the real stories of people. You
259 know like what happened when let's say I believe for the European
260 perspective Bucha is quite familiar. We remember these horrific photos.
261 We're not thinking about the numbers that we've seen in the TV. We are
262 thinking about women laying on the ground. After you are reading the story
263 about the woman and how she was living, who she was, what she was doing
and
264 so on.

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265 You can also open the discussion about children. You are realizing that it
266 is a new generation, it is the future of the country. And it is not
267 something even discussable. Everyone can get this topic. So, I believe that
268 bringing the real story of people and providing the understanding through
269 it. We recently had an event at Ukrainian embassy in Prague. We were
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270 presenting the movie produced in collaboration with Polish colleagues in
271 Warsaw. It is called "People 2024". And they were representing the horrors
272 of the war in different stories. The movie is about five different stories
273 of people. There are women, there are children. And they are focusing on

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these aspects because they are more understandable and you can feel empathy.

The main problem is the lack of empathetic approaches. To understand the situation so that it is not just somewhere far away. That it is still happening. I believe it is the main key here. The storytelling necessary to make people understand better what is really happening.

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Again, our main problem right now we have in Ukraine is the lack of media presence in Europe. It's not enough in comparison what's happening in Ukraine. And unfortunately, we have lack of journalists. We have lack of capabilities and financial resources. Especially in comparison with the Russian colleagues that are maintaining this huge propaganda machine. You can hear their narratives in Europe.

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We are working on it. We are doing the research. And when you see these messages in some political campaigns or repeated by specific leaders, you are just wondering how it is working for them. And for sure it will have the impact on the civil society as well. Primarily on civil society I would even say.

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FN: Do feel like there is the possibility to put the pressure from below? That the civil society is pressuring their own politicians to influence elections and the narratives that are dominant in the European Union?

..4.2. Civil Society & N

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AV: I mean, everything is working in unity again. Civil society is playing a big role, especially in the European context. And for sure the voices of people are working. They will be heard. So, the media is playing a huge role, especially in Ukrainian context. Because again what we are hearing from the news is specific data. Again for people for the research or something but you are not hearing the real stories.

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There is a project of Ukrainian colleagues. It is a movie about abduction. It's called "Abduction Childhood" if I remember that correctly. It's about stories of children that were taken by force in occupied cities. From Ukrainian areas to Crimea first and afterwards to Russia. And they tried to put them to the host families. These children, they are telling the horrific treatment. How they lock them in the basement, put pressure on them. The mental pressure. And when you realize the reality is like that. When the child is telling you, it's different. You analyze that differently in your head.

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FN: To make it personal. To put create empathy. I'm pretty sure that you have quite an intergenerational experience talking to diplomats in Europe who tend to be at least above 40. Do you see a difference in how you can communicate to people of your age compared to the older generations that actually have the influence in Europe?

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AV: I mean as I'm working since 2023 for the organization Neighbours East as Young European Ambassador. We had the opportunity to represent our ideas

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to our European colleagues and the Western world. This is providing a lot of opportunities. But in fact, it is quite difficult to hear these voices for people who are not familiar with international relations, not operating or not studying in this field. I am sure this is a problem in the European context as well. And yeah, you can present your ideas. You can have the

..3.1.1. Challenges

..3.1.1. Challenges

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conference about that. It will be a really nice conversation. But where is the outcome? What is the decision making here? Where could actions really be implemented?

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I don't believe that voices of young people are heard on the same level. However, the European Union is providing many programs for young people. It

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is trying to help young people to integrate into this international relations field in general. And it is providing a lot of opportunities to collaborate with European leaders. To connect them with the youth. I think, it's something truly great. I really appreciate the opportunity to be part of it. But I believe that there's a big gap between both sides. But I mean they are trying to do what they can. There are plenty of projects. However, the problem is to spread the information about the projects itself. But in fact, there's many programs that are trying to integrate young people, young leaders. And to connect them to their future colleagues. Let's say it like that.

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FN: Alright. So you see that there starts to be like a willingness?

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AV: Actually, it's changing a lot right now. It's pretty dynamic. And I think right now we can see the role of young people and their efforts. Ideas that are completely new or topics that are currently unheard. It's truly valuable and so dynamic. I mean, in the past 3 years plenty of programs just appeared. And young people carry that effort themselves. I am

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also trying to implement such programs for young people. To integrate them.

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To build a community. Because again, in unity we have the power.

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FN: Absolutely. As young ambassador as one of the roles. Do you see advantages and disadvantages by talking about these topics as a person of your age?

..5.4. Lessons Learned

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AV: I mean for me it's something that I believe is my path. Because when I was sitting in occupied city, I didn't have even access to mobile data. I had no connection. I was fully isolated from the reality itself. And no one could hear me. Neither my voice nor the voices of many like me. And right now, I have opportunity to speak up. I can tell people what it is like actually to live like that. What is actually happening in Ukraine. And why it is important. So, to answer all of these questions: I believe it's really important right now for young people to be heard.

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For example, the program Neighbours East is connecting people from Eastern Europe. It is not only Ukraine but there are Belarusians, Armenians, Azerbaijanis, Georgians and so on. We are connecting these people. This program was created for young people to become part of this journey in future. I think this is really important. Neighbours East also exists for the West part of Europe as well.

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FN: What do you think is one of your major learnings in your skillset in negotiating and explaining these issues? What do you feel like is something you learned in the last 2 years?

..5.4. Lessons Learned

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AV: First of all, how you have to understand the context. The European

..5.4. Lessons Learned

364 context. How you convey the information. Something I learned: People want
365 to hear what they are interested in. So, you have to shape the information
366 according to the context you are operating in. This is really important. I
367 believe that is a problem for many representatives from Ukraine. Because
368 when they provide the information and the reality that we are living in,
369 for sure it is horrific. But it is important to understand it here in this
370 context. That is has value. Because by understanding they can make a
change.
371 They want to be part of the journey and they are willing to help.

..5.4. Lessons Learned

372 It is really important to understand the context of people you talk to. Why
373 this could be beneficial or why they could help other people. Why it is so
374 important what is happening in Ukraine. Why it is so important to talk
375 about it. How we can make the change. Realizing the context is something
376 truly important for both sides. I would say there are so many takeaways in
377 our work. What we are bringing to the table is really important even on the
378 small scale. As the head of the Horizon Research Program, I have 12
379 students who are working in the same sphere. This is an important
380 experience for them. They learn to communicate. For example, the
interviews
381 I mentioned. It is a small secret but I will tell here. We will have an
382 interview with the Prime Minister of the Czech Republic, the British
383 Council, and other diplomats. These are people you cannot reach by
yourself.
384 It is something where you have to operate in the community. Where you
have
385 to represent a research program or some European initiative. At the same
386 time this could be important and interesting for the leaders as well.

387 There has been a lot of learnings in the last years. But it is pretty much
388 the communication directed to the target audience. And the messages that
389 you want to provide. Because it is something really important that you have
390 to translate from your language and your way of speaking to a language
that
391 the person could understand.